

Non Existence of Non-trivial Solutions to the Diophantine Equation $x^p \pm y^q = z^r$

Nicholas J. Daras

Hellenic Military Academy, Department of Mathematics and Engineering Sciences,
16673 Vari Attikis, Greece. Email:njdaras@sse.gr

Abstract. *We prove that there is no non-trivial solution to the Diophantine equation $x^p \pm y^q = z^r$ provided that $\min\{p, q, r\} \geq 3$ and $\gcd(x, y, z) = 1$.*

Key Words and Phrases: *Diophantine equation, Generalized Fermat equation, Beal's Conjecture, Dirichlet's Theorem on arithmetic progressions, Bezout's Identity, greatest common divisor*

AMS Subject Classification: 11A05, 11A41, 11D09, 11D41, 11N32

In the early twentieth century, David Hilbert presented twenty-three great mathematical problems which featured main directions of scientific research throughout the period that followed ([11,12]). By analogy, in 2016, John F. Nash and Michael Th. Rassias gave a list with seventeen, currently unsolved problems in modern mathematics, in the belief that these problems are expected to determine several of the main research directions at least during the beginning of the XXI century ([17]). The third problem in the series of this list refers to the exploration of the possibility of extending Fermat's Last Theorem.

Even before achieving a proof of this Theorem ([18]), various generalizations had already been considered, to equations of the shape $Ax^p \pm By^q = Cz^r$, for fixed integers A, B and C . In this direction, the Theorem of Henri Darmon and Andrew Granville states that *if A, B, C, p, q and r are fixed integers with $p^{-1} + q^{-1} + r^{-1} < 1$ the generalized Fermat equation $Ax^p + By^q = Cz^r$ has at most finitely many solutions in coprime non-zero integers x, y and z ([9]).* However, as is made clear through those mentioned by Michael A. Bennett, Imin Chen, Sander R. Dahmen and Soroosh Yazdani ([2, 17]), except the solutions identified by Preda Mihăilescu in the Catalan equation ([16]) and the solutions derived from some elementary numerical identities where at least one among the exponents p, q and r equals 2, in all other known cases, *there is no non-trivial solution of this equation once we assume that $A = B = C = 1$ and $p, q, r \geq 3$ ([1,3,4,5,8,10,14]).* In this direction, *Beal's Conjecture* states that *if $\min\{p, q, r\} \geq 3$ and $\gcd(x, y, z) = 1$, there are no non-trivial coprime solutions to the generalized Fermat equation with constant coefficients $x^p + y^q = z^r$ ([8, 17]).* To date, many computational attempts produced strong evidence that such a claim may be correct ([15]). Given the many promising indications, in [6] we were able to give a rigorous and brief *constructive proof* of this conjecture.

The main purpose of the present paper is to extend this constructive proof to the most general case of the equation $x^p \pm y^q = z^r$, by showing that *if $\gcd(x, y, z) = 1$, this Diophantine equation has only trivial integer solutions whenever the exponent p is greater than two and the other two exponents q and r are greater than or equal to two ([7]).* In particular, we will reaffirm *Bell's Conjecture* and give a new proof of *Fermat's Last Theorem*.

To prove our assertion, let us suppose that, on the contrary, there are three integer exponents $p \geq 3$, $q \geq 2$, $r \geq 2$ and six positive integers A , x , B , y , C and z satisfying an equation of the form $x^p \pm y^q = z^r$. We will always assume that the products x , y and z represent *coprime* numbers ($\gcd(x, y, z) = 1$). It is clear that in such a case *only one of the natural numbers x , y and z can be an even number*. So, without loss of generality, we will assume that $x = \text{even}$, $y = \text{odd}$ and $z = \text{odd}$.

Given any m, n, λ in \mathbb{Z}^+ (the set of all positive integers), $\lambda = \text{odd}$ and $\sigma \in \mathbb{Z}^+ \setminus \{1\}$, put

$$\tau_{m,n} := -y^{\sigma q-4}n(2m+n) + \tau_0, \text{ with } \tau_0 := \lambda y^{q-2}.$$

Adopting this definition, it is clear that $\tau_{m,n}$ is an integer and the following result applies.

Proposition 1. *There exist $m_*, n_* \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, for which the corresponding expressions $Cz^2 \mp By^2\tau_{m_*,n_*}$ represent prime numbers.*

Proof. Since $\gcd(\mp y^{\sigma q-2}, \mp [z^2 \mp \tau_0 y^2]) = 1$, an application of Dirichlet's Theorem on arithmetic progressions in its basic form, shows that there are infinitely many prime numbers π such that $\pi \equiv \mp [z^2 \mp \tau_0 y^2] \pmod{(\mp y^{\sigma q-2})}$. In particular, there exist infinitely many natural numbers X such that the integers $\pi \equiv \mp y^{\sigma q-2}X + [z^2 \mp \tau_0 y^2]$ are prime numbers. Since τ_0 , y and z are odds, the numbers X are also odd and, therefore, they can be represented as differences of two squares $([X+1]/2)^2$ and $([X-1]/2)^2$. Taking $X, m_* \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ and $\nu \in \mathbb{Z}^+$ so that $X+1 = 2m_*$ and $X-1 = 2\nu$, we get $y^{\sigma q-2}(m_*^2 - \nu^2) = \pm [z^2 \mp \tau_0 y^2] \mp \pi$ for a prime number π and, therefore, the integer $n_* = m_* \pm \nu$ will be a root of the equation $y^{\sigma q-2}n_*^2 + 2m_*y^{\sigma q-2}n_* \pm [z^2 \mp \tau_0 y^2] \mp \pi = 0$. We infer $\pm y^{\sigma q-2}n_*^2 \pm 2m_*y^{\sigma q-2}n_* + [z^2 \mp \tau_0 y^2] - \pi = z^2 \mp y^2\tau_{m_*,n_*} - \pi = 0$ and, thus, the proof of *Proposition 1* is completed. \square

We may now draw the following first conclusion.

Proposition 2. *Let m_* and n_* be as in Proposition 1, so that the inequality*

$$\tau_{m_*,n_*}z^{r-2} - y^{q-2} \neq \pm 1$$

is fulfilled. The following result applies:

$$\gcd(x^{p-2}, \tau_{m_*,n_*}z^{r-2} - y^{q-2}) = 1.$$

Proof. To get a contradiction, suppose there is a natural number $\varrho > 1$ such that $x^{p-2} = \varrho c_1$ and $\tau_{m_*,n_*}z^{r-2} - y^{q-2} = \varrho c_3$ for some integers c_1 and c_3 . Multiplication of the first equation by x^2 gives

$$x^p = \varrho(c_1x^2),$$

while multiplication of the second one by $\pm y^2$ and z^2 gives

$$\pm y^2\tau_{m_*,n_*}z^{r-2} \mp y^q = \pm\varrho(c_3y^2) \Rightarrow \pm y^q = \pm y^2\tau_{m_*,n_*}z^{r-2} \mp \varrho(c_3y^2) \text{ and}$$

$$\tau_{m_*,n_*}z^r - z^2y^{q-2} = \varrho(c_3z^2) \Rightarrow \tau_{m_*,n_*}z^r = z^2y^{q-2} + \varrho(c_3z^2),$$

respectively. Adding the first two equations, we get $x^p \pm y^q = \varrho(c_1x^2 \mp c_3y^2) \pm y^2\tau_{m_*,n_*}z^{r-2}$ or, by hypothesis, $z^r = \varrho(c_1x^2 \mp c_3y^2) \pm y^2\tau_{m_*,n_*}z^{r-2}$ which can equivalently be stated as

$$z^{r-2} [z^2 \mp y^2\tau_{m_*,n_*}] = \varrho(c_1x^2 \mp c_3y^2).$$

Similarly, subtracting the third equation above from the multiple of the first one by τ_{m_*,n_*} , we get $\tau_{m_*,n_*}(x^p - z^r) = \varrho(\tau_{m_*,n_*}c_1x^2 - c_3z^2) - z^2y^{q-2}$, or, by hypothesis, $\mp\tau_{m_*,n_*}y^q = \varrho(\tau_{m_*,n_*}c_1x^2 - c_3z^2) - z^2y^{q-2}$ which can equivalently be written as

$$y^{q-2} [z^2 \mp y^2\tau_{m_*,n_*}] = \varrho(\tau_{m_*,n_*}c_1x^2 - c_3z^2).$$

Having regard to *Proposition 1*, from the last two relationships, it follows that ϱ divides both z^{r-2} and y^{q-2} . This contradicts the requirement $\gcd(x, y, z) = 1$ under the assumption that $x^p \pm y^q = z^r$. So, it is impossible to have $\gcd\{x^{p-2}, \tau_{m_*,n_*}z^{r-2} - y^{q-2}\} > 1$, and the proof is completed. \square

Remark 1 If $p = 2$, then the proof of *Proposition 2* would be impossible to start properly, for the reason that in such a case the first of our original hypotheses (namely $x^{p-2} = \varrho c_1$) would have no sense, since it should be degenerated into the false relationship $1 = \varrho c_1$, with $\varrho, c_1 \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $\varrho > 1$. \square

We are now in position to give the main result of this paper.

Theorem 1. *There is no non-trivial solution to the equation $x^p \pm y^q = z^r$, provided that $\min\{p, q, r\} > 2$ and $\gcd(x, y, z) = 1$.*

Proof. Let m_* and n_* be as in *Proposition 1*. Let also $U, V, \tilde{U}, \tilde{V} \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}$ with $U\tilde{V} - \tilde{U}V \neq 0$. Then the system

$$(\mathbb{S}_{\mathbb{Z}}) \begin{cases} (U)X + (-V)Y + (\tau_{m_*,n_*}V)Z = \pm 1 \\ (\tilde{U})X + (-\tilde{V})Y + (\tau_{m_*,n_*}\tilde{V})Z = \pm 1 \\ (x^2)X + (\pm y^2)Y + (-z^2)Z = 0, \end{cases}$$

with determinant $(U\tilde{V} - \tilde{U}V)(z^2 \mp y^2\tau_{m_*,n_*}) \neq 0$, has unique solution

$$X = \mp \frac{V - \tilde{V}}{U\tilde{V} - \tilde{U}V},$$

$$Y = \mp \frac{(U - \tilde{U})Cz^2 + (V - \tilde{V})\tau_{m_*,n_*}x^2}{(U\tilde{V} - \tilde{U}V)(z^2 \mp y^2\tau_{m_*,n_*})} \text{ and}$$

$$Z = -\frac{(U-\tilde{U})By^2 \pm (V-\tilde{V})x^2}{(U\tilde{V}-\tilde{U}V)(z^2 \mp y^2 \tau_{m^*,n^*})}.$$

By Proposition 2, $\gcd(x^{p-2}, \tau_{m^*,n^*} z^{r-2} - y^{q-2}) = 1$, so an application of Bezout's Identity guarantees that the Diophantine equation $(x^{p-2})u + (\tau_{m^*,n^*} z^{r-2} - y^{q-2})v = \pm 1$ can be solved in \mathbb{Z}^2 . Given any fixed partial integer solution $(u, v) \in \mathbb{Z}^2$ of this equation and $\kappa \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, $\ell \in \mathbb{Z}^+$, $\kappa \neq \ell$, let us take the induced solutions $U, V, \tilde{U}, \tilde{V} \in \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0\}$ defined by

$$\begin{aligned} U &:= u + \kappa (\tau_{m^*,n^*} z^{r-2} - y^{q-2}), & V &:= v - \kappa x^{p-2}, \\ \tilde{U} &:= u + \ell (\tau_{m^*,n^*} z^{r-2} - y^{q-2}) & \text{and } \tilde{V} &:= v - \ell x^{p-2}. \end{aligned}$$

Observe that $U, V, \tilde{U}, \tilde{V} \neq 0$. Further, since $U\tilde{V} - \tilde{U}V = \pm(\kappa - \ell) \neq 0$, it is easily seen that, for this option, the unique solution of the system $(\mathbb{S}_{\mathbb{Z}})$ is exactly $(X, Y, Z) = (x^{p-2}, y^{q-2}, z^{r-2})$. But, on the other hand, considering the above-mentioned expression for this unique solution, we also get $X = x^{p-2}$, $Y = (-z^2)D + (x^p \tau_{m^*,n^*})E$ and $Z = (\mp y^2)D + (x^p)E$, where we have used the notation

$$D := \frac{\tau_{m^*,n^*} z^{r-2} - y^{q-2}}{z^2 \mp y^2 \tau_{m^*,n^*}} \text{ and } E := \frac{1}{z^2 \mp y^2 \tau_{m^*,n^*}}.$$

In other words, adopting this formulation, we found

$$y^{q-2} = (-z^2)D + (x^p \tau_{m^*,n^*})E \text{ and } z^{r-2} = (\mp y^2)D + (x^p)E.$$

Since, from our assumption, $x^p = Cz^r \mp y^q$, it follows immediately that the system of equations

$$\begin{aligned} (1 - Ez^2)Z \pm (Ey^2)Y &= \mp Dy^2 \text{ and} \\ (\pm \tau_{m^*,n^*} Ez^2)Z + (-E\tau_{m^*,n^*} y^2 \mp 1)Y &= \pm Dz^2 \end{aligned}$$

would have solution $(Z, Y) = (z^{r-2}, y^{q-2})$. But, this is impossible to hold true, since the determinant of this system is zero and both lines representing it must in any case not be identical, otherwise we would have $D = 0$ and $z^2 = -y^2$ which is absurd. We therefore conclude that there is no non-trivial solution to the Diophantine equation $x^p \pm y^q = z^r$. \square

The proof given above was only for the case where $p, q, r \geq 3$. However, it is easy to see immediately that this proof can be extended to the case $p \geq 3$ and $q = 2$ or $r = 2$ when $x = \text{even}$ and $y, z = \text{odd}$. More specifically, in exactly the same way, it turns out that *there is no non-trivial solution to the Diophantine equations:*

$$\begin{aligned} x^p \pm y^2 &= z^r, \text{ if } p \geq 3, r \geq 3, \\ x^p \pm y^q &= z^2, \text{ if } p \geq 3, q \geq 3 \text{ and} \\ x^p \pm y^2 &= z^2, \text{ if } p \geq 3, \end{aligned}$$

whenever the number x is even and $\gcd(x, y, z) = 1$.

Remark 2 The necessary condition $\gcd(x, y, z) = 1$ is essential, because otherwise the Diophantine equation $x^p \pm y^q = z^r$ may have infinitely many integer solutions. If, for instance, the exponent r is any common multiple of p and q

increased by one, say $r = \mu p + 1 = \eta q + 1$, this equation has non-trivial integer solutions of the form $x = a(x^p + y^q)^\mu$, $y = b(x^p + y^q)^\eta$ and $z = x^p + y^q$, whenever $a, b, c \in \mathbb{Z}$, even if p (either q) equals 2 ([13]). \square

Remark 3 The argument in the proof of *Theorem 1* seems to use only linear algebra and seems not to use that x, y, z are integers if you allow all auxiliary entities like u, v, τ_{m^*, n^*} to be real (or complex) numbers. Where on the proof of *Theorem 1* did we use integrity of x, y, z ? Where does the argument break down in the case when x, y, z is any real or complex solution (consider, for example, in place of τ_{m^*, n^*} , any real or complex number τ such that E is defined)?

Let us give an answer to this reasonable question and describe a reason why this proof does not extend to the case of real or complex numbers. First, notice that, in \mathbb{Z} , the specific selection of the parameter τ_{m^*, n^*} within the set of prime integers is essentially compatible for our purposes, since, besides other crucial properties, this particular choice meets the two necessary conditions

$$D \neq 0 \text{ and } E < \infty.$$

In the context of integers, it is *impossible* (: in fact, it is “*forbidden*”) to exist a value for the parameter $\tau = \tau_{m^*, n^*} \in \mathbb{Z}$ satisfying $D = 0$, since any such option would imply $y^{q-2} = \tau_{m^*, n^*} z^{r-2}$, and, thus, the integer z would divide the integer y , in contrast to the straightforward consequence $\gcd(y, z) = 1$ of our basic hypothesis $\gcd(x, y, z) = 1$.

Unlike to the case of integers, any attempt to extend a similar reasoning into a wider set, like the field \mathbb{R} of real numbers or the field \mathbb{C} of complex numbers, is doomed to fail. Failure is due to the fact that, if the quantities τ, y and z are taken so that $\tau z^{r-2} - y^{q-2} \neq 0$ within \mathbb{R} or \mathbb{C} , then any condition of the form $\gcd(x^{p-2}, \tau z^{r-2} - y^{q-2}) = 1$ does no matter, because in such a case the pairs (u, v) satisfying the equation $(x^{p-2})u + (\tau_{m^*, n^*} z^{r-2} - y^{q-2})v = 1$ would be the (infinite) points of an entire line. In fact, *the flexibility provided by the “free choice location” of the parameter τ everywhere within the set $\mathbb{K} \setminus \{y^{q-2}/z^{r-2}\}$ ($\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}$) is drastically reduced if $\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{Z} \setminus \{0, \pm 1\}$, due to the role of $\tau = \tau_{m^*, n^*}$ in the parametrization of the equation $(x^{p-2})u + (\tau_{m^*, n^*} z^{r-2} - y^{q-2})v = 1$ (:the case where one of the numbers y, z is equal to 1 has already been studied in [16]). This drastic restriction disappears if $\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}$, since then, given any two numbers $y, z \in \mathbb{K} \setminus \{0, \pm 1\}$ and any two values of the numerical parameters $q, r \in \mathbb{K} \setminus \{0\}$ satisfying $z^r \neq y^q$, it is always possible to find a $\tau \in \mathbb{K}$ such that $y^{q-2} = \tau z^{r-2}$ ($\Leftrightarrow D = 0$) with $z^2 \neq \tau y^2$ ($\Leftrightarrow E \in \mathbb{K}$). Indeed, observe that, due to the inequality $z^r \neq y^q$, we can also write $z^2 \neq [y^{q-2}/z^{r-2}]y^2$. Defining $\tau := y^{q-2}/z^{r-2}$, it is clear that $z^2 \neq \tau y^2$ and $E \in \mathbb{K}$, in such a way that $y^q = \tau z^{r-2}y^2$. Hence $z^r - y^q = z^r - \tau z^{r-2}y^2 = z^{r-2} [z^2 - \tau y^2] = z^{r-2}/E$, i.e., we conclude that $z^r - y^q = z^{r-2}/E$.*

This, in particular, implies that, for each $p \in \mathbb{K} \setminus \{0\}$, the number $x := (z^{r-2}/E)^{1/p} \in \mathbb{K} \setminus \{0, \pm 1\}$, together with the given $y, z \in \mathbb{K}$, satisfies the equation $x^p + y^q = z^r$.

The above discussion is summarized in a general methodological framework of finding a typical solution (x, y, z) of the equation $x^p + y^q = z^r$ in \mathbb{K}^3 ($\mathbb{K} = \mathbb{R}, \mathbb{C}$), in accordance with the following four successive standard algorithmic steps:

- **Step 1:** Given $z, y \in \mathbb{K} \setminus \{0, \pm 1\}$ and $q, r \in \mathbb{K} \setminus \{0\}$ such that $z^r \neq y^q$, take $E := [z^2 - \tau y^2]^{-1}$, with $\tau := y^{q-2}/z^{r-2}$ ($\Leftrightarrow D = 0$).
- **Step 2:** Since $y^{q-2} = \tau z^{r-2}$, the following typical relationship applies:

$$z^r - y^q = z^{r-2}/E.$$

- **Step 3:** For each $p \in \mathbb{K} \setminus \{0\}$, define $x := (z^{r-2}/E)^{1/p}$.
- **Step 4:** The numbers x, y and z satisfy the equation $x^p + y^q = z^r$ in $\mathbb{K}^3 \setminus \{0\}$.
□

Corollary 1 (*Affirmation of Beal's Conjecture*) *There is no non-trivial solution to the generalized Fermat equation $x^p \pm y^q = z^r$, provided that $\min\{p, q, r\} \geq 3$ and $\gcd(x, y, z) = 1$.* □

We conclude with two direct consequences of this last result.

Corollary 2 (*Fermat's Last Theorem*) *There is no non-trivial solution to the Fermat equation $x^p + y^p = z^p$, provided that $p \geq 3$ and $\gcd(x, y, z) = 1$.* □

Corollary 3 (*Irrationality of Binomial Expansions*) *If $p, q, r \geq 3$, there is no $(x, y) \in \mathbb{Z}^2$ with $\gcd(x, y) = 1$ satisfying $(x^p + y^q)^{1/r} \in \mathbb{Q}$.*

Proof. Suppose there is a rational number $(P/Q) \in \mathbb{Q}$, with $P, Q \in \mathbb{Z}$ and $\gcd(P, Q) = \gcd(x, y, P) = 1$, satisfying $x^p + y^q = (P/Q)^r$. Obviously, from this last relationship it is directly deduced that $P^r = Q^r(x^p + y^q)$. So, from the fact that $\gcd\{P, Q\} = 1$, it is therefore directly deduced that $P^r \mid (x^p + y^q)$, which means that there is a $k \in \mathbb{Z}$ satisfying $(x^p + y^q) = kP^r$. It follows that $P^r = Q^r k P^r$, which implies that $Q^r k = 1$. But, this only applies if $Q = k = 1$. In such a case, we would have $x^p + y^q = P^r$ and also $\gcd(x, y, P) = 1$, which, in view of *Corollary 2*, is impossible to hold true. □

References

1. M. A. Bennett: The equation $x^{2n} + y^{2n} = z^5$, *Journal de Théorie des Nombres de Bordeaux* 18 (2006), 315–321.
2. M. A. Bennett, I. Chen, S. R. Dahmen and S. Yazdani: Generalized Fermat equations: a miscellany, *Int. J. Number Theory* 11 (2015), 1 – 28.
3. N. Bruin: The Diophantine equations $x^2 \pm y^4 = \pm z^6$ and $x^2 + y^8 = z^3$, *Compositio Math.* 118 (1999), 305 – 321.
4. N. Bruin: Chabauty methods using elliptic curves, *J. Reine Angew. Math.* 562 (2003), 27 – 49.
5. N. Bruin: On powers as sums of two cubes, ANTS IV, Leiden 2000, 169 – 184, *Lecture Notes in Comput.Sci.* 1838, Springer 2000].

6. J. Daras: A Constructive Proof of Beal's Conjecture, <https://arxiv.org/abs/1903.03613>
7. J. Daras: On the Unsolvability of the Diophantine Equation $Ax^p \pm By^q = Cz^r$, preprint
8. H. Darmon: The equation $x^4 - y^4 = z^p$, C.R.Math.Rep.Acad.Sci. Canada 15 (1993), 286 – 290.
9. H. Darmon and A. Granville: On the equations $z^m = F(x, y)$ and $Ax^p + By^q = Cz^r$, Bull.London Math. Soc. Textbf 27 (1995), 513 – 543.
10. H. Darmon and L. Merel: Winding quotients and some variants of Fermat's Last Theorem, J. Reine Angew. Math. 490 (1997), 81 – 100.
11. M. Hazewinkel, ed. (2001) [1994]: Hilbert problems, Encyclopedia of Mathematics, Springer Science + Business Media B.V. / Kluwer Academic Publishers, ISBN 978-1-55608-010-4.
12. D. Hilbert: Mathematical Problems, Bulletin of the American Mathematical Society 8(10) (1902), pp. 437-479. (Also, Bulletin (New Series) of the American Mathematical Society 37(4), pp. 407-436, S 0273-0979(00)00881-8. Article electronically published on June 26, 2000. Text on the web: <http://www.ams.org/journals/bull/2000-37-04/S0273-0979-00-00881-8/S0273-0979-00-00881-8.pdf>) Earlier publications (in the original German) appeared in Göttinger Nachrichten, 1900, pp. 253-297, and Archiv der Mathematik und Physik, 3dser., vol. 1 (1901), pp. 44-63, 213-237.
13. R. Jakimczuk: Diophantine Equations. Elementary Methods, International Mathematical Forum, 12(9) (2017), 429 – 438.
14. A. Kraus: Sur l' équation $a^3 + b^3 = c^p$, Experiment.Math.7 (1998), 1 – 13.
15. R. D. Mauldin: A Generalization of Fermat's Last Theorem: The Beal Conjecture and Prize Problem, Notices of the AMS 44 (11) (1997), 1436 – 1439.
16. P. Mihăilescu: Primary Cyclotomic Units and a Proof of Catalan's Conjecture, J. Reine Angew. Math.572 (2004), 167 – 195.
17. J.F. Nash and M.Th. Rassias(eds.): Open Problems in Mathematics, Springer (2016), 543 pages.
18. A. Wiles: Modular elliptic curves and Fermat's Last Theorem, Ann. Math. 141 (1995), 443 – 551.